

Thermodynamics of the Interaction of Bivalent Transition Metal Ions with Methyl Thymol Blue

I. P. SARASWAT, C. L. SHARMA** and ANITA SHARMA

Vikas Nagar, 134/3, University of Roorkee, Roorkee

Manuscript received 1 January 1978, revised 2 May 1978 accepted 6 June 1978

The formation constant, enthalpy and entropy changes for the formation of 1 : 1 chelates of bivalent transition metal ions with methyl thymol blue have been determined. The analysis of the thermodynamic quantities shows that two acetate groups, nitrogen and phenolic oxygen are coordinated to the metal.

METHYL thymol blue has been extensively used as an indicator¹⁻⁹ or a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination¹⁰⁻¹⁷ of a large number of metal ions but there are divergent views regarding the number of species in solution and the chelating sites in the reagent¹⁸⁻²⁰ (For brevity methyl thymol blue would be written as MTB throughout the text). Further, thermodynamic data on the interaction of MTB with transition metal ions is meagre. Through this communication an attempt is being made to partially fill this gap. We report thermodynamic stability constants for the interaction of MTB with bivalent Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn ions, ΔG , ΔH and ΔS values for the interactions are also reported because ΔH values reflect the number and strength of bonds and the relative entropy changes can be useful in detecting the concomitant changes in the structure of the complexes formed due to metal ions-MTB interactions.

Experimental

The metal solutions were made from analytical reagent grade BDH or equivalent quality chemicals and were standardised by complexometric titrations, MTB was purified as described by Yoshino et al²¹. Carbondioxide free potassium hydroxide solution was used for pH metric titrations which were carried out in a double walled glass titration vessel provided with inlet and outlet tubes circulating water at constant temperature (variation $\pm 0.1^\circ$) from a thermostat. After each addition of alkali titrant, the solution was stirred well with magnetic stirrer and allowed to stand for attainment of equilibrium.

Keeping ionic strength constant at 1.0, 0.5, 0.25 and 0.1 with KNO_3 , the following sets of titrations (expanded scale pH-meter ECIL make was used throughout) were performed against standard KOH (0.025 M) at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$ and $40 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

- (i) For metal chelates
 - (a) 20.0 ml MTB (0.001 M)+5.0 ml. metal ion (0.001 M)+5.0 ml. KNO_3 (0.25 M to 1.5 M)
 - (b) 20.0 ml. MTB (0.001 M)+5.0 ml. H_2O +5.0 ml. KNO_3 (0.25 M to 1.5 M)
- (ii) For ligand dissociation constant
 - (a) 25 ml. HClO_4 (0.002 M)+25 ml. H_2O vs 0.02 M, KOH
 - (b) 25 ml. HClO_4 (0.002 M)+25 ml. MTB (0.005 M) vs 0.02 M KOH
 - (c) 25 ml. MTB (0.005 M) vs 0.04 M KOH

Stability constants were then determined at three different ionic strengths by Bjerrum's method²², from these an extrapolation to zero ionic strength was possible. Ligand dissociation constants were determined by the method of Irving and Rossotti²³.

The enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) changes were calculated from the temperature coefficient of the thermodynamic equilibrium constant for 1 : 1 metal ligand complex.

The accuracy for pK values reported in Table 1 is ± 0.02 units and the accuracy of $\log K$ values given in Table 2 is ± 0.3 log units, therefore, the precisions of ΔH and ΔS are $\pm 0.5 \text{ K cal mole}^{-1}$ and $\pm 2 \text{ cal mole}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-1}$.

Results and Discussion

The job's method of continuous variation and Bjerrum's pH-metric method indicated the formation of 1 : 1 complex. The dissociation constants (pK values) for the ligand are given in Table 1. They are in fairly good agreement with the reported values^{24,25}. Table 2 summarises the values of $\log K$ at 30 and 40° for 1 : 1 metal ligand complexes along with the values of ΔH and ΔS .

**Correspondence to be made to Vikas Nagar, 134/3, University of Roorkee, Roorkee.

TABLE—1 DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF MTB IN 1.0 M, 0.5 M, 0.25 M AND 0.1 M KNO₃ AT 30 AND 40°.

Temp°C	Ionic strength	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₃	pK ₄	pK ₅
30°	1.0 M	3.00	3.28	3.77	7.40	11.13
	0.5 M	3.00	3.28	3.77	7.35	11.00
	0.25 M	3.00	3.28	3.75	7.24	10.52
40°	1.0 M	2.95	3.10	3.65	7.00	10.98
	0.5 M	2.95	3.10	3.58	6.85	10.45
	0.25 M	2.05	3.05	3.55	6.74	10.32
	0.1 M	2.95	3.00	3.50	6.70	10.28

TABLE—2 THERMODYNAMICAL STABILITY CONSTANTS (LOG K), ΔF, ΔH (IN KCALS MOLE⁻¹) AND ΔS (IN KCALS MOLE⁻¹ DEG⁻¹) VALUES AT 30° FOR 1:1 METAL COMPLEXES OF MTB.

Thermo-dynamic parameters	Temp °C	Mn(II)	Fe(II)	Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Zn(II)
log K	30	7.82	10.75	12.28	12.45	13.84	13.11
	40	7.70	10.62	12.14	12.31	13.66	12.95
-ΔG	30	10.84	14.90	17.02	17.26	19.18	18.17
	40	11.02	15.21	17.39	17.63	19.59	18.54
-ΔH		5.20	5.63	5.85	6.07	7.80	6.93
ΔS		18.61	30.59	36.86	36.93	37.55	37.09

The stability of the chelates Mn(II) < Fe(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II) is in agreement with the Irving William rule. The obvious regularity seems to be in the entropy term ΔS, which decreases with increase of ionic radius (with Cu(II) as an exception). Further, it appears that the stability of the MTB complexes is mainly due to ΔS values which are large and positive, though the ΔH terms make contribution to the stability and there are variations in ΔH values.

The value of enthalpy change increases from Mn(II) to Cu(II) with a drop at Zn(II). The contribution to the total change in enthalpy by the acetate groups is generally very small and sometimes endothermic as in metal dicarboxylate complexes involving melonate, succinate, acetate etc. Similar type of behaviour is also found in bulky molecule, for example, in metal complexes of *trans*-1,2-diaminocyclohexane-N, N' tetraacetic acid. The contribution to the total enthalpy change in such cases becomes still smaller because of steric hindrance caused by the bulky groups or rings attached to the iminodiacetic acid^{2a}. The exothermic values given in table 2 are fairly high and can not be accounted by only metal-nitrogen bond. Secondly there is a very small variation along the series of transition metal complexes which are more negative than the values reported for the complexes of iminodiacetic acid²⁷ where only two acetates and one nitrogen atom are coordinated with the metal. This indicates the involvement of phenolic oxygen atom in coordination because of which there will be lack of strain in the chelate rings as OH group is more loosely bonded to the metal atom, which may, in turn allow the other metal-nitrogen and metal-oxygen bonds to become stronger. This will also produce a lack of

charge on the site which lessens electrostatic repulsion. The bonding between phenolic oxygen atom and metal is also supported from their electronic spectra. The maximum value of $\bar{n} \approx 1.0$ was obtained beyond the pH=5.0. The colour of the solution containing metal and dye in the ratio of 1:1 changed from yellow to blue for Co(II), green-blue for Ni(II), blue-purple for Cu(II) and purple-blue for Zn(II) in the pH range 5-10. A new maxima (λ_{max}) at 600 nm is observed for the dye solution in this pH range. These sharp colour changes suggest change in the electronic structure of the sulphophthalein group and may be attributed to combination of metal ion with the dissociated phenol group. At pH 5-10 depending on the metal, the absorbance remains almost constant indicating complete formation of 1:1 complex.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. B. L. Gupta, Scientist in DRP, (BARC) Bombay for useful suggestions.

References

1. F.W.E. STRELOW and E. V. S. TOERIEN, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1966, 36, 189.
2. F. KREZA and V. D. MALKOVIC, *Glas. Hem. Technol. Bonse Hercegovine*, 1969, 17, 23.
3. K. STANISLAW and K. VYTRAS, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1968, 33, 3726.
4. C. CHIN-CHI, *Tai. Ni. Chi. Shu.*, 1971, 6, 253.
5. C. CHIN-CHI and C. CHAO-TEH, *Tai. Ni. Chi. Shu.*, 1973, 8, 215.
6. N. GENKICHI and H. WADA, *Talanta*, 1973, 20, 829.
7. K. C. SRIVASTAVA and S. K. BANERJI, *Chem. Age. India*, 1969, 20, 606.
8. Z. STANISLAW and L. LOMOZIK, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1976, 21, 692.
9. Y. K. TSELINSKII and A. B. NIKOLAEVSKAYA, *Zh. Prikl. Khim.*, 1974, 47, 1991.
10. E. A. BASHIROV and A. M. AYUBOVA, *A. Zerb. Univ. Ser. Khim. Nauk.*, 1971, 3, 24.
11. O. TOSHIO, *Bunseki Kagaku*, 1972, 21, 1359.
12. C. ERNESTO, P. VINEENZO, M. ANTONIOL and B. FABRIZIO, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1972, 102, 911.
13. G. A. BUTENKO, A. S. GRZHEGORZHEVSKII and I. G. STURRE, *Vop. Khim. Tekhnol* 1972, 27, 128.
14. G. A. BUTENKO, A. S. GRZHEGORZHEVSKII and I. G. STURRE, *Vop. Khim. Tekhnol*, 1972, 27, 131.
15. Z. STANISLAW and L. LOMOZIK, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1976, 21, 692.
16. N. TOSHIKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan*, 1968, 41, 1619.
17. K. C. SRIVASTAVA, *Bull. Inst. Chem., Acad. Sinica.*, 1972, 19, 61.
18. O. A. TATAEV and L. G. ANEIMOVA, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1971, 26, 184.
19. K. BORISLOV, K. DONKA and N. PETRANA, *Talanta*, 1968, 15, 525.
20. A. DOADRIO, A. G. CARRO, and D. F. MARIA, *Quim. Anal.*, 1975, 29, 331.
21. Y. TAKASHI, I. H. KUWANO and T. I. KATSUYA, *Talanta*, 1969, 16, 151.
22. J. BJERRUM, 'Metal Ammine formation in Aqueous solutions' P. HASSE and SON, Copenhagen, 1941.
23. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
24. J. KORBL and B. KAKAE, *Chem. Listy*, 1957, 51, 1680.
25. Y. TAKASHI, I. H. MURAKAMI, and S. K. MEGUMI, *Talanta*, 1974, 21, 211.
26. G. ANDEREGG, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1963, 46, 1833.
27. G. ANDEREGG, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1964, 47, 1801.